

Interview with Illustrator Yoshiyuki Sadamoto

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Yoshiyuki Sadamoto, a professional illustrator and manga artist, is one of the founding members of the animation studio Gainax and, together with Hideaki Anno, was responsible for the creation of the *Neon Genesis Evangelion* series. He is also the manga artist for the project.

Sadamoto has also contributed to other series, such as *FLCL*, and animated feature films like *Ōritsu Uchūgun: Honnêamise no Tsubasa* (*Royal Space Force: Wings of Honnêamise*) and *Toki wo Kakeru Shōjo* (*The Girl Who Leapt Through Time*) by Mamoru Hosoda, as well as video games, including the *.hack//* series. On the occasion of his visit to FicZone 2016, we had the honour of interviewing him in Granada. Without further ado, here is the interview with the artist.

Interview with Yoshiyuki Sadamoto

Cool Japan: Mr Sadamoto, you were one of the key members in the founding of Daicon Film, which later became Gainax. How did you experience this process? What was your role in establishing the studio?

Yoshiyuki Sadamoto: When I was at university in Osaka, there were classmates who had a project in mind and wanted me to be part of it. I worked with them, and later the idea of *Evangelion* emerged. After conceiving the idea, I was offered a chance to work in Tokyo. While we were immersed in the project, we received an offer from Bandai. From there, the idea grew.

During my studies, Anno [Hideaki] was working on the first *Macross* series while we were in our second year. He invited me to participate, even though I didn't know much about animation.

Still, it seemed interesting to work on it; it was a challenge, something new to learn. The following year, the Daikon IV event was held, where I participated in the short film that we, the members, presented. Later on, I worked on *Ōritsu Uchūgun: Honnêamise no Tsubasa* (王立宇宙軍 オネアミスの翼), already designing characters for that film.

Original illustration by Yoshiyuki Sadamoto for *Royal Space Force: Wings of Honnêamise* (1987)

I have countless memories of that feature film. When *Honnêamise* came about, I was already working in a studio, which was not yet Gainax. By that time, I had already graduated from university. They were teaching me the work I would do in that studio, but Gainax contacted me and kept insisting that I join them. They asked how much I was earning back then—which was not much—and offered me a little more.

I was a novice, so I earned what would have been about one thousand euros a month for you [around 860 GBP/1150 USD]. They said, “If you earn 120,000 yen, then we will give you 130,000.” I went with them without knowing if it would be good or not, but I

wanted to take the chance. I was very young and just starting out.

CJ: As you mentioned, you began your journey as an animator almost by chance working on *Macross*, and later learned the craft under the guidance of great masters. How was this learning experience? Which series were most influential for you, especially at the beginning of your career? And regarding reading manga today, which series are your favourites, both manga and anime?

YS: Authors such as Leiji Matsumoto and Gō Nagai. They are the foundation for me, the base; authors I read in my youth. Later, I was influenced by people like Hayao Miyazaki and Katsuhiro Ōtomo. I do not know many other authors, but perhaps I should also mention the illustrator Hisashi Sakaguchi, although not many people know this. I loved his work since I was young. Whenever I start a new work, I keep them in mind. The thing is, there are so many authors.

CJ: More than twenty years have passed since you began the *Evangelion* project, and it is now a true icon in the manga and anime industries. What are your thoughts on the enormous phenomenon that has formed around your work? Additionally, in recent years, you have been collaborating with Studio Khara on the new *Rebuild of Evangelion* films. How has it been to revisit the work you did for the series? How did the idea for *Neon Genesis Evangelion* come about?

YS: After working on *Ōritsu Uchūgun: Honnêamise no Tsubasa*, Gainax gradually grew as a studio, and later we worked on the *Evangelion* series, which was the most successful project I have been involved in and the work to which I have devoted more than twenty years of my life and career.

The idea to create Evangelion arose simply from wanting to do something new. We conceived the animation and the manga; I decided to take on the manga, and Gainax would handle the animation. At first, I was drawing the manga faster than the animation series was progressing at the time, so I also took on the character design for the animation and worked on other projects.

I have been working with Evangelion for twenty years; I no longer want to think about the series. My work on the films has been very limited, mostly at the design level, but I am not involved beyond that. I do not know much about the plot or what they will do with Evangelion. Anno is working on *Godzilla* and Evangelion. *Godzilla* will premiere next July [2016], but I do not know any more about the dates for Evangelion or any other details.

CJ: Do you believe that working with Hideaki Anno has influenced your vision of how to present a story to the viewer? For example, focusing on small details in a scene, which might initially seem incidental but actually explain the situation the characters are experiencing.

YS: I cannot speak on that. I would have many anecdotes to share, but I prefer not to.

CJ: As we understand it, you will also be participating in the production of the sequels to *Furi Kuri —FLCL—* a series that is very beloved here in Spain. How did this project come about? What can we expect from these new series?

YS: Initially, I worked with Gainax on *FLCL*, and later I have done some work for Production I.G, but only at the level of consulting for the designs. Gainax does not currently hold the rights to *FLCL*, as Production I.G has acquired them. The upcoming *FLCL* releases will be produced by I.G, and I have nothing to do with decisions beyond consulting on character design.

Illustration by Yoshiyuki Sadamoto for *FLCL* (2000)

The thing is, people think I am more involved in the project than I actually am. The reality is that I.G only involves me in matters related to character design; I'm afraid I don't know anything else about the production.

CJ: We would like you to tell us about your technique. We see that you have a very personal and detailed drawing method. Could you tell us what tools you use and a little about your approach when tackling a work?

YS: Most of my work is in manga format, so I primarily use traditional techniques—paper, pencil, etc.—. Also in animation, as I have been working in anime for over twenty years. I mostly use pencil, like every mangaka, since I started.

I also learned to use colour and specialised in colour illustrations, which are worked more slowly than manga. Until now, for manga, I used screentones, which had to be cut to size and glued. Nowadays, there are tools that make that work easier. With manga, I can still progress much faster and produce more drawings despite the use of screentones.

CJ: Regarding that last point, we would like your opinion on digital art. We see that you almost exclusively stick to analogue and traditional methods. Is this purely an artistic choice? Or personal preference?

We see colleagues like Yū Honda or Shunji Suzuki creating digital art for the *Evangelion* series. As the lead designer, did you work closely with them to advise them? We find it very admirable that you continue to draw traditionally in these times.

YS: Well, regarding digital art... at the moment I am learning to use new tools to apply colour digitally. Previously, I had to use screentones for my manga, but now I am learning to incorporate the computer into this task, for example to add darker or lighter tones, light, and shadow. It is much more comfortable, but I am still learning.

I have always worked feeling part of the studio. It is a feeling I discovered while working in animation. Being part of a team where everyone is important: the illustrators, the artists, the sound team... I think that if I failed, or my work was missing, or theirs, the series would fail. But I only focus on my own work.

I always concentrate on making my work as good as possible. I push myself and constantly think things like, “this failed,” and I want to do better in my next work. I always want to take on different projects. I do not have a favourite work of my own, because I believe that whatever I do next has to be better than what I have already done.

Illustration by Yoshiyuki Sadamoto for *Neon Genesis Evangelion*

My relationship with digital art has been difficult, but not for personal reasons. I began with a love–hate relationship towards digital art and had to work with the computer for professional reasons. I am learning. I have wanted to learn it, and I am making an effort to improve.

For instance, when it comes to applying colour... I have used the Ugee G3 digital tablet extensively for digital art. Using it to apply colour—the aspect for which I use digital art the most—was challenging from the start because my memory for computing matters is very limited.

Normally, when I am relaxed, I save my progress every ten minutes, but sometimes, when I am fully focused on an illustration and working enthusiastically... in those moments when you tell yourself, “Alright, I’m working, everything is going well,” I forget to save for hours...

And suddenly, something happens, or an error appears, and all my work disappears in an instant... [laughs] Six hours of work, sometimes.

This has happened to me on multiple occasions, sometimes even around three in the morning, and I have woken up my family unintentionally, who also had to get up early the next morning [laughs].

CJ: Recently, you have worked as a designer on some films by director Mamoru Hosoda. How does Yoshiyuki Sadamoto approach a new project with Hosoda? Of all the films you have participated in, which production is your favourite?

YS: It is very complicated [laughs]. Yes, the most important work for me that I have done with Mamoru, and the one that has marked me the most, is the first film in which I collaborated with him: *Toki wo Kakeru Shōjo* [*The Girl Who Leapt Through Time*]. Because it was a different director and studio outside of Gainax. This has always been something I enjoyed doing: experiencing what it feels like to work with a different team of people from the one I already know.

Hosoda travelled to where I live to request my collaboration in person. He told me he needed my drawings for his film. He came specifically because he wanted me on the project. That impressed me deeply, and I felt very honoured. Hosoda has always wanted to work with me. His latest work, *Bakemono no Ko* [*The Boy and the Beast*], has been very successful, even without my participation.

I think they will continue without me, and I believe they can do so perfectly. The last production went very well without my involvement. When I first worked with Hosoda, I again felt that curiosity about what it would be like to work for another studio, and I was interested.

CJ: Hosoda is a director who is gaining significant recognition nowadays. Having worked with him, what was the experience of meeting Mamoru Hosoda like? Can you tell us something more personal about him?

YS: My experience with Mamoru was very fun and unusual. Occasionally, in Japan, when discussing a project, we meet at a hotel and work or talk about work and business. They call you, invite you to collaborate on a project, and you meet that person. We like meeting in nice hotels.

Although I fear Hosoda [laughs]... enjoys drinking far more than the hotels themselves, and he told me he had chosen a wonderful, splendid hotel. He selected a hotel for our meeting, but to my surprise, it was a capsule hotel, so we did not work in the room, as it was a tiny space [laughs].

I had a lot of fun, but there was a problem. Spending a night there... well, staying in a capsule is fine. The problem was different, aside from the room itself: Mamoru... SNORES [laughs].

I thought about throwing him out because I could not sleep near him [laughs]! The hotel itself was fine, but not the sleeping area where we had to rest. It is like sleeping in a small capsule for the night. For working, he is a great guy, but he does things like this. Very funny, though.

CJ: How was adapting *Evangelion* into manga? Did you have complete freedom, or did you have to follow specific guidelines?

YS: They told me to work as I wanted in the manga. We added details, like introducing Mari [Illustrious Makinami] —the character from the Rebuild films— and that she was in love with Yui Ikari. This idea came up spontaneously between the Khara writer and me, just to try something. I had total freedom with the manga.

I decided on aspects of the manga script that have been perfectly preserved, such as Shinji saying a line at the beginning of the series, in the first chapter, twenty years ago: that he “had no dreams, no ambitions, no plans for the future,” etc. At the end of the manga, he repeats this phrase, but it carries a completely different meaning. Ideas like that I conceived for the manga, and they reached the reader exactly as I had initially intended.

CJ: What aspects of your personality or experiences can be found in characters like Naota or Shinji? Which character do you most enjoy drawing?

YS: I identify with my characters, yes. They carry something of me, although I do not always seek it consciously. Especially with Shinji Ikari. I wanted to portray Shinji growing in a short time, showing his transition from a child to an adult, all in a brief period, and still being a child at a complicated age.

That was my intention from the very beginning. In the final chapters of the manga, there are scenes where Shinji appears a little more mature, especially emotionally; we see Shinji changed. He is particularly based on my personal experiences.

To attend university —I’m from Yamaguchi Prefecture, in southern Honshū, so I had to move to Tokyo— I had to leave my family behind. I felt very lonely and kept telling myself, “I have to do this,” just as Shinji tells himself in *Evangelion*. Also, when I first arrived in Tokyo, it was snowing heavily, like at the end of the manga.

Illustration by Yoshiyuki Sadamoto for the cover of the final volume of the *Neon Genesis Evangelion* manga

I felt internally that I had to act as an adult. I wanted to convey that feeling and situation in the *Evangelion* manga. I always wanted Shinji to show that inner struggle of having to act as an adult while still a child. It’s something you will have seen in *Evangelion*.

I felt like Shinji in my youth. I worked on *Evangelion* for twenty years, and I respected that idea until the end of the manga.

When it comes to *Evangelion* characters... I really like drawing Kensuke Aida, because he is different from the rest. Kensuke also has parts of me, like having goals and daring to try new things and being fascinated by them. I like Kensuke very much for his personality too.

I like Shinji a lot, but he always overthinks everything. Kensuke is good because he acts more proactively, thinking less before doing things; he decides at the last moment. I also love that he encourages other characters, like Shinji himself. I also enjoy drawing characters like Azure Kite, from the .hack// video games, which I also worked on.

CJ: Evangelion is full of religious references, nods, or homages to directors like Stanley Kubrick. Considering that, given the implicit promotion most of your works have, which encourages the viewer to delve into the underlying themes, we would like to know if this is something you consciously aim for when creating your works.

YS: Lately I have been thinking about cinema and Stanley Kubrick. I do like his work, and I have seen all his films. I enjoy cinema a lot, I watch many movies, but I don't consciously try to reference one director or another, or one film or another.

Speaking of religion, you are probably mostly Christians, I imagine. We Japanese, being Buddhists/Shintoists —meaning we have different religions— have a very different view of religion. For us, “God is out there,” although we don't think he has to help us or intervene directly in our lives. Well, when we are in trouble, we do pray in Japan: “Oh, Kami-sama. Oh, Kami-sama...” [laughs]

I took ideas from the Gospel for the title —*Evangelion*— from Adam and Eve, many names and aspects of various religions, mostly Christian. But no one on the team was Christian, or at least I don't know. That has nothing to do with me, nor was it our intention to do it with a specific purpose. When I reference something like that, I don't do it for a special meaning, only because I like it or find it interesting. Many ideas and concepts in *Evangelion* were included indirectly, without any intention beyond that.

I don't think of God the way you might in the West. As an Asian, my view of God is very different from yours. I don't think there is a God who wants us all to be happy, because when you look at the world, you see good things, but you also see war, suffering, hunger... For me, God is very selfish.

I don't look to the sky thinking of God. Maybe Kubrick's perspective is something I have addressed unconsciously. Perhaps there is some similarity between him and me, and I have referenced him and other directors, though I hadn't stopped to think directly about paying homage to one director or another. I do like many directors, including Kubrick.

The same happens with music. I only work as an illustrator and I always need to listen to something, a background song, but I don't stick to one theme or genre. I always have music in the background while I work.

For example, if I've seen a movie that moved me before starting work, I then look for the soundtrack and play it; the same goes for a singer or a band I like, or a song that caught my attention. Hearing them influences my work in drawing, though I don't know how or to what extent, but it does.

CJ: To conclude, now that you have finished your longest work to date, do you intend to return to manga? What new challenges await, Yoshiyuki Sadamoto sensei? What will we see next bearing your signature?

YS: Right now I am drawing a manga, in fact, but I'm also working on a film, and collaborating on an animation project. In addition, I've been approached to collaborate on a mobile game. I'm working on these four things at the same time. Each project is completely different, so I have to switch my mindset constantly

Some of Sadamoto's characters, as featured in the author's art book *Yoshiyuki Sadamoto Art Collection Carmine*, published in 2010

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A special mention goes to his interpreter, Michie Yamaya, whose excellent work and patience made it possible to successfully conduct the interview. She allowed us to speak again with Mr. Sadamoto to complete the questions we had remaining during his conference and afterwards.

The Aljibe at FERMASA, Granada. The venue where we interviewed Yoshiyuki Sadamoto sensei. Taking photographs of him was not permitted.

Since the beginning of the interview had to be conducted in a round-table format, the various press outlets mutually agreed to use everyone's questions if necessary. For this reason, I must also thank my fellow journalists from the other attending media, such as Otaku Music Radio —very kind to me— and, especially, Alfa Beta Juega, particularly Miguel Ángel, who on several occasions gave me his turn so I could ask my questions instead.

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Sources

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